

The other side of neurotransmission: nomenclature for receptor cells

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A suffix for emission but not reception

In the 1930s, Henry Dale introduced the terms ‘cholinergic’ and ‘adrenergic’ to classify nerves by their neurotransmitter identity (H. Dale 1935; H. H. Dale and Feldberg 1934).

“...it seemed to me desirable to have a terminology enabling us to refer to a nerve fibre in terms of the chemical transmission of its effects, without reference to its anatomical origin; and, on this functional basis, I proposed to refer to nerve fibres and their impulses as ‘cholinergic’ or ‘adrenergic’, as the case might be.” (H. Dale 1936)

Drawing from Greek *ergon* (work) with *-ic* (relating to), this construction has proven an enduring, convenient way to refer to neurotransmitter-releasing cells. The use of the ‘-ergic’ suffix expanded as new neurotransmitters were discovered. After dopamine’s neurotransmitter function was established in the late 1950s (Montagu 1957; Carlsson, Lindqvist, and Magnusson 1957), the term ‘dopaminergic’ arose in the early 1960s (Sourkes and Poirier 1966). The same occurred with ‘serotonergic’, ‘GABAergic’, and dozens of other systems (Gosselin, Moore, and Milton 1962; Nicoll 1972). However, while we have recognizable adjectives for neurons that emit particular neurotransmitters, the descriptions of cells that *receive* these signals remain variable and verbose. Current literature reveals striking *ad hoc* terminology; for example, dopamine-receptive cells may be described as “dopamine-sensitive neurons,” “dopamine-receptor neurons,” or “neurons expressing dopamine receptors” (Juárez Tello et al. 2024; Locke et al. 2018; Kim and Narayanan 2019; Mueller et al. 2020). Such verbosity and variability reveals a nomenclature gap.

Established precedents point to the ‘-ceptive’ suffix

A possible solution already appears in the literature. The English word ‘receptor’ was adopted by immunology and physiology in the early 20th century (Oxford English Dictionary 2025). Around the same time, the terms ‘nociceptive’ and ‘proprioceptive’ were coined to describe specialized neuronal systems in terms of their sensory inputs (Sherrington 1906). The term ‘adrenoceptor’, a contraction of ‘adrenergic receptor’, has been in use since the 1960s at the latest (Chahl and O’Donnell 1969). In the 1970s, ATP/adenosine receptors were dubbed ‘purinoceptors’ (Burnstock 1978, 2018), a term

that became official pharmacological nomenclature (Fredholm et al. 1994). Recent literature points to the need for a suffix to describe receptor-bearing cell types, with the use of ‘GABAceptive’ and ‘dopaminoceptive’ (Liu et al. 2022; Montalban et al. 2022; Ambroggi et al. 2009; Lee, Schwab, and McGeer 2011). All the above terms use the ‘-ceptor’, ‘-ceptive’ or ‘-oceptive’ suffixes, which derive from the Latin verb *capere*, meaning to take, seize, capture.

Table 1. Proposal for adjectives to indicate that a cell receives a transmitter type.

Neurotransmitter/Neuromodulator	Producing Neurons	Receiving Neurons
Epinephrine/Adrenaline	Adrenergic	Adrenoceptive
Acetylcholine	Cholinergic	Cholinoceptive
GABA	GABAergic	GABAceptive
Dopamine	Dopaminergic	Dopaminoceptive
Glutamate	Glutamatergic	Glutamoceptive
Glycine	Glycinergic	Glycinoceptive
Serotonin	Serotonergic	Serotonoceptive
Oxytocin	Oxytocinergic	Oxytocinoceptive
Vasoactive intestinal peptide (VIP)	VIPergic	VIPceptive
Adenosine	Adenosinergic	Adenosinoceptive
Histamine	Histaminergic	Histaminoceptive

Proposal to generalize the ‘-ceptive’ suffix

Here, I propose the generalization of the suffix ‘-ceptive’ to indicate that a cell type contains receptors for a transmitter, neuromodulator, or neuropeptide. Conjunctions will often replace the terminal vowel with ‘o’, i.e. ‘-oceptive’. I suggest formulations as follows:

- Drop final vowel before adding suffix: ‘dopamin(e)’ → ‘dopaminoceptive’
- Use contractions where unambiguous: ‘noradrenaline’ → ‘noradrenoceptive’
- For acronymic names: ‘NPY’ → ‘NPY-ceptive’

A partial list of proposed terms is given in Table 1. This system would provide clear terminology for neurotransmitter reception. That is, ‘dopaminergic neurons’ release dopamine, while ‘dopaminoceptive neurons’ receive dopamine signals. This will enable simpler cell-type descriptions, improve text-search efficiency, and reduce confusion. The

advent of single-cell sequencing and connectomics intensifies the need to clearly describe cellular types. Just as the ‘-ergic’ suffix has enabled the precise specification of neurotransmitter-releasing cells, words using the ‘-ceptive’ suffix could serve as convenient references to cell types expressing certain neurotransmitter receptors.

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